

Connect to the Data Access Broker (DAB) as a data owner

The **Data Access Broker (DAB)** helps data providers manage access to their datasets more efficiently, securely, and consistently. The DAB interprets each dataset's access conditions and provides automated advice on data access requests. This saves providers considerable administrative time while leaving the final decision fully in their hands.

By connecting to the DAB:

- the process of requesting and granting access becomes much simpler;
- all access requests are automatically logged and tracked;
- providers can use **ODISSEI's established access workflows**;
- and datasets can be securely shared via the **SANE Trusted Research Environment (TRE)**.

⇒ Try the most recent [Proof of Concept of the DAB](#).

The following steps should be followed to connect to the Data Access Broker.

1. Define access conditions

Each dataset should have clear access conditions, expressed in **ODRL (Open Digital Rights Language)**. ODRL is an open standard that allows rights, permissions, and obligations to be **machine-readable**.

The DAB **interprets these conditions** and checks whether a researcher's access request satisfies them. If all obligations are met (for instance, the requester is affiliated with a Dutch research institution and will use a secure environment), the DAB issues a **positive recommendation** to grant access. If desired by the provider, the DAB can also automatically approve an access request.

Access conditions are expressed as an **ODRL profile**.

Recommended practice:

*ODISSEI recommends defining the **SANE Trusted Research Environment** as the default access route, restricted to **staff of Dutch research institutions** (SURF members). This setup – based on long-standing experience with CBS Microdata – combines strong data protection with minimal administrative effort. ODISSEI is in the process of publishing the ODRL profile and license of this template access route, so that data providers can easily adopt it.*

2. Set up a metadata endpoint

The DAB retrieves dataset information and access conditions (the ODRL profile) through a **metadata endpoint** – typically the repository where metadata are already published. This endpoint should provide machine-readable metadata (e.g., in DCAT format) that include the ODRL conditions. This enables the DAB to automatically identify which rules apply to each dataset.

Read the [separate explanation of how to set up a metadata endpoint](#).

3. Determine the level of the access request and the PID

An access request typically applies at the **dataset or DOI level**. The data provider should ensure that the dataset's metadata are **findable in a repository** (see the [metadata manual](#)), and that a **DOI** or other **Persistent Identifier (PID)** is assigned.

In some cases, researchers may request access to a **subset** of a dataset (e.g., specific years or variables). Then a **separate PID** should identify that subset so the DAB can correctly match the request to the relevant subset of the data.

4. Map your access process to the DAB

The DAB is designed to **fit existing provider workflows**. Providers keep their internal review and approval processes but connect them to the DAB's generic workflow steps (request, review, decision, delivery). This makes the process **transparent and partially automated**, reducing manual handling while keeping decision-making local.

The result: less administration, more consistency, and clearer communication between researchers and providers.

5. Set up a communication channel

The DAB automatically tracks all requests, decisions, and pending actions, ensuring that communication and recordkeeping are centralized.

You can choose to use the DAB as the interface to handle requests, or to connect the DAB to your existing request communication channel. In the latter case, you should establish a fixed communication channel for DAB-related access requests, such as:

- a general email address (e.g. *access-request@data-provider.nl*), or
- an internal helpdesk or Slack channel.

6. (Optional) Enable data transfer via SANE

If desired, the DAB can automatically link approved access requests to the **SANE Trusted Research Environment (TRE)**. Once access is granted, the dataset can be securely transferred to SANE, allowing the researcher to begin analysis immediately – without data ever leaving the provider's infrastructure.

The provider decides whether and when this option is enabled.

Contact

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